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o-Cyanodiphenyl has been hydrolysed to give *o*-phenylbenzoic acid with the formation of the *o*-phenylbenzamide as the intermediate product. A new method for the preparation of *o*-phenylbenzaldehyde has been described and the preparation of *o*-phenylcinnamic acid accomplished for the first time.

Kaiser (*Annalen*, 1890, 257, 100) claimed to have prepared *o*-phenylbenzoic acid by the hydrolysis of *o*-diphenylnitrile with alcoholic potash. The hydrolysis of this nitrile as mentioned also by Braun and Manz (*Annalen*, 1929, 463, 274) presents unusual difficulties and the present authors did not succeed in getting the acid by the direct hydrolysis of the nitrile either with alcoholic potash or sulphuric acid, but obtained the corresponding amide on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash while with sulphuric acid the reaction proceeded one step further and large quantities of fluorenone were obtained. The amide obtained with alcoholic potash on further hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid was almost quantitatively converted into the corresponding acid

Pictet and Gonset (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1897, I, 413) and Fanto (*ibid.*, 1899, I, 424) claimed to have prepared *o*-phenylbenzaldehyde by the pyrolysis of a mixture of the calcium salts of *o*-phenylbenzoic acid and formic acid. The details are, however, meagre and incomplete.

Having prepared the corresponding nitrile by an easy method (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 27) the present authors attempted to prepare the aldehyde by Stephen's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1874). Repeated attempts in this direction have failed to give the aldehyde inspite of different modifications including those mentioned by King and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 273) and King, Liguori and Robinson (*ibid.*, 1933, 1476). King, L'Ecuyer and Openshaw (*ibid.*, 1936, 352) have also recorded similar experiences in preparing the corresponding aldehydes from *o*-naphthonitrile and *o*-tolunitrile.

The authors next adopted a method described by Houben and Doscher (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4576). An ethereal solution of *N*-methylformanilide has been made to react with the magnesium derivative of *o*-iododiphenyl. The resulting compound is hydrolysed by means of dilute hydrochloric acid. On extraction with ether and fractional distillation in vacuum *o*-phenylbenzaldehyde has been obtained in fairly good yield.

Phenylcinnamic acid has also been obtained in good yield by the condensation of the aldehyde with malonic acid (*cf.* Pandya and Vahidy, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 4A, 154).

The authors are at present engaged in preparing derivatives of this cinnamic acid with a view to utilising it as the starting material for a new synthesis of phenanthrene and its derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Phenylbenzamide.—*o*-Cyanodiphenyl (2 g.) was gradually added to alcoholic potash (20%, 25 c.c.) and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 3 hours. The alcohol was recovered and water was added to the residue when a crystalline product was obtained, which was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from hot water as colourless needles, m.p. 177°, yield 1.8g.

(82%). (Found: C, 79'20; H, 5'54; N, 7'04. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{11}ON$: C, 79'17; H, 5'58; N, 7'10 per cent).

o-Phenylbenzoic Acid.—*o*-Phenylbenzamide (1 g.) was heated for 2 hours with hydrochloric acid (20 c. c., 1:1). A green oily liquid was produced, which solidified on cooling. The supernatant hydrochloric acid was decanted and the solid dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. The solution was acidified and the precipitate crystallised from 40% alcohol, m.p. 113'5°, yield 0'76 g. (76%). (Found: C, 78'83; H, 4'94. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{10}O_2$: C, 78'78; H, 5'5 per cent).

o-Phenylbenzaldehyde.—*o*-Iododiphenyl (1 mol., 28 g.), dissolved in absolute ether (100 c.c.), was treated with magnesium turnings (2'5 g.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen, stirred with a mechanical stirrer and freshly distilled methyl formamide (13'5g.), prepared from monomethyl aniline and formic acid dissolved in absolute ether (35 c.c.), was added in the course of 2 hours. A vigorous reaction set in and a copious white precipitate was obtained. Any ether evaporating off was made up by the addition of ether from time to time. The stirring was continued for 1 hour in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The magnesium compound produced was decomposed by adding large quantities of crushed ice and hydrolysed by acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous portion further extracted with ether. The combined ethereal extracts were dried over calcium chloride, the ether distilled off and the residue distilled at 150°/7 mm. as a light coloured oil, which darkens on keeping for a few days, yield 12'2 g. (67%).

o-Phenylbenzaldehyde-phenylhydrazone, prepared as usual, crystallised from alcohol as golden yellow crystals, m.p. 139°. (Found: C, 83'84; H, 5'82; N, 10'24. $C_{19}H_{16}N_2$ requires C, 83'81; H, 5'88; N, 10'30 per cent). It gives a crystalline bisulphite compound with sodium bisulphite.

o-Phenylcinnamic Acid.—A mixture of *o*-phenylbenzaldehyde (3'6 g.) and malonic acid (3 g.) containing five drops of dry pyridine were heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. During the last hour the reflux condenser was replaced by an air condenser to allow the resulting water to be expelled. On cooling a precipitate was obtained, which was collected and washed with ice-cold water containing a few drops of dilute sulphuric acid. It was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and reprecipitated with dilute sulphuric acid. It crystallised from alcohol as colourless light crystals, m.p. 202°, yield 3'22 g. (72%). The acid is soluble in ether, alcohol and chloroform. (Found: C, 80'41; H, 5'31. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 80'37 H, 5'34 per cent).